

EFFECT OF GAMIFICATION ON THE ATTITUDES OF THE STUDENTS TOWARD MATHEMATICS AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 33

Issue 2

Pages: 186-196

Document ID: 2025PEMJ3151

DOI: 10.70838/pemj.330205

Manuscript Accepted: 12-10-2024

Effect of Gamification on the Attitudes of the Students toward Mathematics and Academic Performance

Jesalyn M. Lazarte,* Sharon L. Apohen
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to investigate the effect of gamification on the attitudes of the students towards Mathematics and academic performance of Grade 9 students. The attitudes of students were assessed using a ATMI- Likert scale before and after the intervention, with both the experimental and control groups exhibiting neutral attitudes towards mathematics. Academic performance was measured through pre-test and post-test scores, revealing a significant improvement in the experimental group, reaching a very satisfactory level, while the control group achieved a satisfactory level. Statistical analysis indicated no significant change in attitudes towards mathematics between the groups post-intervention. However, a substantial increase in academic performance was observed in the experimental group, with a mean score jump from 10.06 to 25.33, significantly higher than the control group's score of 17.82. These findings suggest that while attitudes remained neutral, the gamification intervention had a notable positive impact on the academic performance of students in the experimental group compared to the control group. Overall, the intervention had a more significant impact on academic achievement in comparison to the control group. The incorporation of gamification into mathematics education for students in the ninth grade has a great deal of promise for improving both students' attitudes about the subject as well as their academic achievement. Educators can create engaging learning experiences by utilizing the motivational components of games.

Keywords: *gamification, attitudes, students, academic performance*

Introduction

The advancements in technology in the 21st century have resulted in the diversification of learning profiles among contemporary students (Eleyyan, 2021). The learning profiles exhibit variations based on the age of the learners (Avcu & Er, 2020). Nevertheless, it is worth noting that educational games are deemed significant for all types of learning profiles, as supported by several studies (Valiente et al., 2020). Furthermore, research has provided evidence of the educational benefits of games and game-like forms, particularly for students in primary and secondary schools (Yaşar, 2018).

Researchers discovered that mathematics curricula and the individualistic nature of mathematics, in which pupils work alone, inhibit learning. As a result, increasing student enjoyment in mathematics learning is an important method for addressing topic disengagement. Innovative teaching strategies, such as gamification, that give positive mathematical learning experiences may aid in improving students' arithmetic ability

Upon reviewing the relevant research (Kim, 2021), it becomes evident that the integration of gamification holds potential for implementation within the context of a fifth-grade mathematics curriculum.

In contrast, Lanuza (2019) incorporated traditional Filipino games as part of a gamification strategy for instructing college-level mathematics courses. The utilization of points and levels as components within the game was seen to be an inventive approach to enhancing students' academic performance. However, it was noted that this technique may have certain limitations when applied to specific mathematical courses or subjects. Although there have been instances where the impact of gamification on certain behavioral aspects of education has yielded inconclusive or negligible results, a growing body of literature demonstrates the positive outcomes associated with gamification.

It was suggested that the use of gamification could have an impact on students' attitudes about the course and their academic achievement. As a result, this study has been conducted in this field. The purpose of this study is to look into "The Effect of Gamification on the Attitude of Students in Mathematics and Academic Performance" in order to better understand how introducing gaming aspects into Mathematics instruction can affect students' attitudes toward the subject and their overall academic performance.

By investigating the impact of gamification on student attitudes and academic performance in mathematics, this study hopes to provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of gamified approaches in improving learning outcomes and fostering positive attitudes toward a traditionally difficult subject (Smiderle et al. 2020). The effects of gamification on students' views are the subject of conflicting research at this time. While some studies have not found a substantial effect, others have demonstrated that gamification can increase students' attitudes and participation. To learn more about the circumstances in which gamification works to positively influence students' attitudes, more research is required.

Research Questions

This study aimed to find out the effects of gamification on the attitudes toward Mathematics and Academic Performance of Grade 9

students of Talave Integrated School for S.Y 2023-2024. Specifically, this study aimed to address the following question:

1. What is the attitude of the students towards Mathematics under experimental and controlled groups before and after the intervention?
2. What is the level of academic performance under the experimental and controlled groups before and after the intervention?
3. Is there a significant difference between attitudes of the students towards Mathematics under experimental groups before and after the intervention?
4. Is there a significant difference between attitudes of the students towards Mathematics under the experimental and controlled groups after the intervention?
5. Is there a significant difference between the academic performance of the students in the experimental groups before and after the intervention?
6. Is there a significant difference between the academic performance of the students under experimental and controlled groups after the intervention?

Methodology

Research Design

This study aimed to find out the effect of gamification on the attitudes of the students toward Mathematics and academic performance of Grade 9 students of Talave Integrated School for S.Y 2023-2024. Thus, the researcher employed experimental design.

According to Shrutika Sirisilla (2023), A framework of guidelines and practices known as experimental research design was developed to carry out scientifically-minded experiments with two sets of variables. The first group of variables in this case serves as a constant and is employed to calculate the differences between the second group of variables. Therefore the researcher observes and measures the variables in the study.

Additionally, experimental research is the ideal choice when the aim of the study is to determine how gamification affects students' attitudes toward mathematics and academic achievement. The academic achievement test on the topic from the 2nd Quarter 1st week to 4th week in the mathematics lesson was administered to both groups at the commencement and conclusion of the process. Furthermore, the pre-test and post-test results of the experimental group were compared in order to assess the effect of gamification on students' attitudes toward Mathematics and academic achievement. It was determined whether gamification is beneficial by comparing the post-test academic performance of the experimental group with the control group, as well as the attitudes of the students toward Mathematics an assessment was conducted to measure the participants' attitudes toward the mathematics lesson, both before and after the intervention, for both experimental and control groups.

Participants

The study's participants were Grade 9 students from two sections, Dalton and Volta, who are officially enrolled at Talave Integrated School for the School Year 2023-2024. The students were rated based on their Grade 9 average and randomly sectioned by Grade 9 advisers.

This study contained a sample size of 66 students, including 33 from Section Dalton and 33 from Section Volta. They were chosen among the Grade 9 pupils of Talave Integrated School for the school year 2023-2024. The sample was selected at random from the student body. They were ranked according to their average Math grades in Grade 8. To decide on the gamification and discussion strategy, a coin toss was used.

The table below provides the distribution of the participants per group.

Table 1. Distribution of the Participants per Group

<i>Group</i>	<i>Types of Learning</i>	<i>Number of respondents</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Grade 9-Dalton	Experimental	33	50%
Grade 9-Volta	Control	33	50%
Total		66	100.00

The matched pairing technique involved pairing individuals from the two groups based on relevant variables that could potentially influence the outcome of the experiment. Participants with similar features in both groups were matched and assigned to various circumstances to maximize the similarity between the experimental and control groups.

Instrument

The learners' performance was measured through the administration of pretest and posttest. The researcher employed questions derived from previously administered quarterly exams, in addition to the matching specs table that they came with, which the Division Office provided. These materials were utilized for both the pretest and posttest phases of the study, as they had undergone evaluation and testing. To prevent test familiarity among learners, the item numbers and choices for each question were rearranged. The said instrument was a 40-item. Formative assessments were administered to learners following each lesson to gauge their comprehension of the

material. This information was derived from the Learning Modules/Learner's Packet created by the Department of Education (DepEd) and DepEd Central Office.

The Simegn and Asfaw (2018) investigated the impact of attitude toward Mathematics on Grade 10 and 12 female students' achievement relative to their male counterparts in Wolkite, Ethiopia. They employed a tool to assess mathematical attitudes. Attitudes Toward Mathematics Inventory (ATMI), which measures four elements of attitudes toward mathematics: self-confidence, value, enjoyment, and motivation. The ATMI has been frequently used to assess mathematical attitudes (see Appendix C.1). Several researchers used confirmatory factor analysis to prove the validity and reliability of the ATMI and the results showed a Cronbach's alpha of 0.963. The aforementioned tool was a 40-item, 5-point Likert scale designed to evaluate how gamification affected students' attitudes toward mathematics and their performance in Grade 9.

Procedure

The following steps were taken to guarantee that the information collected for this study will address the stated goals. To conduct the study, the researcher requested permission from the Public Schools District Supervisor (see Appendix B.2.). After receiving approval, the researcher asked the Talave Integrated School Principal for permission to run the study to ninth-grade students. Throughout the study, the researcher herself taught Mathematics 9 for around four weeks.

For this research, the Grade 9 section Volta was set to be a controlled group utilizing the Discussion Method from 10:00 to 11:00 am, and an experimental group using the Gamification method from 11:00 to 12:00 noon. The control group was given instruction in the traditional manner, such as through discussion, while the experimental group received instruction in the form of gamification. After four weeks of classes the same questionnaire will be given to the control group and experimental group. The pre-test and post-test results of the experimental group were compared in order to assess the effect of gamification on students' attitudes toward Mathematics and academic achievement. It was determined whether gamification is beneficial by comparing the post-test academic performance of the experimental group with the control group, as well as the attitudes of the students toward Mathematics.

Experimental Procedures

The experiment was divided into three phases, each with a distinct focus on different areas of the experiment. This strategy was chosen to ensure thorough investigation and knowledge of all aspects involved.

Pre-intervention Phase: Before administering the pretest, the researcher followed the class schedule of Grade 9 pupils. Because their timetable is from 10:00-11:00 am, the control group went first, followed by the experimental group in the afternoon by 11:00-12:00 nn.

Intervention Phase: The researcher interacts with the two groups daily during the intervention phase. The same teacher instructed both groups on the same subject. While the control group was trained through discussion methods, the experimental group was trained through gamification. The table 2 below indicates the subjects that were explored throughout the research period. Topics were aligned to the Budget of Work of the Department of Education School's Division of San Carlos City.

Post-intervention Phase: A post-test was administered after four weeks, or 20 days utilizing the same test and the same with the Attitude toward Mathematics questionnaires as in the pretest. The test results were utilized to calculate the mean scores of the experimental and control groups. It was determined whether gamification is beneficial by comparing the post-test academic performance of the experimental group with the control group, as well as the attitudes of the students toward Mathematics.

Table 2. Competencies and Activity log for 4 weeks of the Research Period

<i>Day</i>	<i>Competencies</i>	<i>Activity Log</i>
1-2	illustrates situations that involve the following variations: (a) direct; (b) inverse; (c) joint; (d) combined	For this day the teacher teach about the introduction of variation. On the next day the teacher let the student depicts scenarios including the following variations: (a) combination; (b) inverse; (c) joint; and (d) direct.
3-4	illustrates situations that involve the following variations: (a) direct; (b) inverse; (c) joint; (d) combined	Teacher review about the previos lesson. Teacher discuss the lesson for the day. For this day the teacher will provide games entitled "Quiz Bee Gamified Powerpoint" topic was about translating into variation statement a relationship between two quantities. The rules of the game are to answer 15 multiple-choice questions (easy, average, and difficult rounds). The team or individual with the most points at the end of the week will win a badge and be included on the scoreboard.
5-7	illustrates situations that involve the following variations: (a) direct; (b) inverse; (c) joint; (d) combined	For this day the teacher make an assessment more enjoyable. Teacher will provide a long quiz thru games entitled as "Ambagan Quiz" The mechanic of the games in every question the 1 member will answer then next person until all of the question on the test paper will finish. The scores of the group is the score of each member of the group. There is a cooperation and need a teamwork in order to have a highest score in quiz. The winning team will be the one with the most points received a badges, and it was recorded in the leader board for this week.

8-9	Translates as a relationship in a variation statement between two quantities supplied by: (a) a value table; A graph is (c) a graph; (b) a mathematical equation, and so on.	Teacher review about the previous lesson. Teacher discuss the lesson for the day. For this day the teacher will provide games entitled “Tama o Mali” topic was about translating into variation statement a relationship between two quantities. The mechanics of the games is to identify whether the given statement is Tama o Mali. Then the group who get highest point will be declare as a winner.
10-11	translates into variation statement a relationship between two quantities given by: (a) a table of values; (b) a mathematical equation; (c) a graph, and vice versa.	For this day the teacher provides games entitled “Car Racing Games” topic was all about variation. The mechanic of the game in every correct answer there is an equivalent point. To make learning is fun and achievable there is an equivalent point scoring in every correct answer. Teacher group the students into 4 to make learning fair and non bias.
12-15	simplifies expressions with rational exponents writes expressions with rational exponents as radicals and vice versa.	Teacher discuss the new lesson about rational exponents. The teacher provide a game entitled as “ Mystery Square”. The mechanics of the game in every correct answer their a hidden image if they correctly simplifies the rational exponents. The group that can correctly answer will choose if what square they will open until all the square will be answered. The group that can guess the mystery image declare as a winner and have an addition points in their Academic performance Task. The team with the highest number of points the winner for this week and received a badges, and recorded in the leaderboard for this week.
16-20	simplifies expressions with rational exponents writes expressions with rational exponents as radicals and vice versa.	Teacher discuss the continuation of the lesson about rational exponents. The teacher provide a game entitled as “ Who wants to be a Millionaire”. The mechanics of the game HOW TO PLAY Answer 15 Multiple Choice questions in a row correctly to win. Use up to 3 lifelines to help you select an answer. The player who can gain a highest point be declare as a winner and have an addition points in their Academic performance Task. The team with the highest number of points is the winner for this week and will received badges, and be recorded in the leaderboard for this week.

Data Analysis

During the analytical phase of this study, various statistical instruments were utilized to analyze the collected data.

The mean was utilized for solving problem 1, which identified the experimental group's pre- and post-test performance utilizing the gamification and discussion strategy.

The mean was used to determine the experimental group's pre-test and post-test performance using gamification and discussion methods in problem 2.

The Fisher Sign Test was utilized to respond to question number 3, which asked about the attitudes of Grade 9 pupils toward mathematics both before and after using gamification.

To answer problem number 4, which asked about the significant difference between attitudes of the students towards Mathematics under the experimental and controlled groups after the intervention, z-test: two sample mean was utilized.

To answer problem number 5, which asked about the significant difference between the academic performance of the students in the experimental groups before and after the intervention, Fisher Sign Test was utilized

To answer problem number 6, which asked about the significant difference between the academic performance of the students under experimental and controlled groups after the intervention, z-test: two sample mean was used.

Ethical Considerations

The study received ethical approval from the Research Ethics Committee. A formal letter stating the participants and asking for permission to access the essential data was written to the superintendent of the schools division and other pertinent authorities. By following established ethical guidelines and legal frameworks, researchers show their commitment to responsible practices, minimizing potential risks and protecting respondents' privacy. Informed consent was obtained after participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, procedures, potential benefits, risks, and rights, including the freedom to withdraw at any time. This section describes the precise steps taken to address ethical issues and make sure the study conforms with applicable regulations, including the Data Privacy Act (RA 10173), as well as professional standards.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the data collected from the study followed by an analysis, and interpretation of the findings. Using statistical tools, the data was analyzed correctly to each statement of the problem. This chapter discussed an experimental study on the Effects of

Gamification on the Attitudes of the students Toward Mathematics and Academic Performance of Talave Integrated School.

Attitude Towards Mathematics of the Experimental Group Before and After the Intervention

Table 3 shows the attitude of Students towards Mathematics under experimental and controlled groups before and after the intervention.

Table 3. Attitude of Students towards Mathematics under Experimental and Controlled Groups Before and After the Intervention

<i>Group</i>	<i>Attitude towards mathematics</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Experimental	Pre-test	33	3.37	Neutral
	Post-test	33	3.36	Neutral
Control	Pre-test	33	3.36	Neutral
	Post-test	33	3.27	Neutral

Based on the table the pre-test score for the experimental group was 3.37 with a neutral interpretation, and the post-test score was 3.36 with the same interpretation. The control group's pre-test score was 3.36, interpreted as neutral, and its post-test score was 3.27, also interpreted as neutral. The result implies that the attitude of the students towards Mathematics remained the same even after the intervention. The same result was acquired in the attitude of students towards Mathematics under control group. The responses are neutral, showing no agreement or disagreement with a balance attitude.

Various studies show mixed outcomes on the effectiveness of gamification in improving attitudes. For instance, while some research indicates that gamification can enhance student engagement and performance, it often does not lead to significant changes in attitudes. For example, Karamert and Vardar (2021) found no substantial difference in attitude scores after implementing gamification in teaching fractions.

Similarly, a study during the COVID-19 pandemic revealed that although both experimental and control groups maintained positive attitudes towards mathematics, there was no significant improvement in the experimental group's attitude post-intervention. The result of this study is closely similar to the claim of neutral response on a Likert scale for testing attitudes toward Mathematics shows that the respondent has neither a strong positive nor negative attitude about Mathematics (Mantero, 2020).

Research suggests that self-confidence, perceived worth of mathematics, enjoyment of mathematics, and motivation all play a role in this. The first quality is self-confidence. Students with neutral attitudes may lack confidence in their math abilities, affecting their performance (Etcuban, 2019). The second factor is perceived value of math: If students do not see the value of math in their lives, it can lead to a neutral attitude and potentially lower performance (Wakhata et al., 2022). The third factor is enjoyment of math: A lack of enjoyment in the subject can impact performance (Siregar et al., 2019). Finally, while motivation alone may not have a substantial impact on performance, a lack of motivation paired with a neutral attitude can be counterproductive to academic success.

Academic performance of students under the experimental and controlled groups before and after the intervention

Table 4 presents the academic performance of students under the experimental and controlled groups before and after the intervention.

Table 4. Academic performance of students under the experimental and controlled groups before and after the intervention

<i>Groups</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
<i>Experimental</i>			
Pre-test	33	10.06	Fairly Satisfactory
Post-test	33	25.33	Very Satisfactory
<i>Control</i>			
Pre-test	33	11.09	Fairly Satisfactory
Post-test	33	17.82	Satisfactory

Table 4 shows that the experimental group has a significant improvement in their scores from the pre-test (10.06) to the post-test (25.33), moving from a fairly satisfactory level to a very satisfactory level. The control group also showed an improvement in their scores from the pre-test (11.09) to the post-test (17.82), but the improvement was not as substantial as the experimental group. The control group moved from a fairly satisfactory level to a satisfactory level.

Both groups showed improvements in academic performance from the pre-test and post-test. However, the experimental group experienced a much larger increase in mean score compared to the control group. The mean score for the experimental group after the intervention (25.33) is notably higher than that of the control group (17.81), indicating a more substantial improvement in academic performance. Overall, the data suggests that the intervention had a more pronounced and effect on the academic performance of the experimental group compared to the control group.

Gamification improves students' academic performance in mathematics by increasing engagement, motivation, and enjoyment, offering quick feedback, boosting active learning, lowering anxiety, and encouraging teamwork. These characteristics combine to create a more effective learning experience, resulting in better academic performance for students.

The result was supported by Türkmen & Soybaş (2019) in their study which determine how gaming use impacts fifth graders' mathematical learning. There were two groups of students involved: twenty-eight in the experimental group (who learned through games) and twenty-two in the control group. Unstructured interviews and classroom observations were employed as part of a mixed-methods study. Pre- and post-test analysis was conducted with a control group using a semi-experimental design and quantitative methodologies. The SPSS analysis of the results shows that the experimental and control groups are similar in terms of both achievement and attitude. Students in the experimental group did marginally better on average than those in the control group.

Difference between the Students' Attitudes towards Mathematics under Experimental Groups Before and After the Intervention

Table 5 on the next page shows the difference between the students' attitude towards Mathematics under experimental groups before and after the intervention.

Table 5. *Difference Between the Attitude of the Students Towards Mathematics under Experimental Group Before and After the Intervention*

<i>Experimental Groups</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Pre-test	33	3.37	Neutral
Post-test	33	3.36	Neutral

Computed value (z): -0.55

P-value: 0.548

Decision : Accept Ho

Interpretation : Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 5 presented the result that the pre-test mean score was 3.37, which decreased slightly to 3.36 in the post-test. The computed value of -0.55 indicates a small decrease in the mean score from the pre-test to the post-test. The null hypothesis is accepted because the p-value of 0.548 is greater than the significance level of 0.05. This signifies that the observed difference in mean scores is not statistically significant at 0.05 level of significance. The effect of gamification to the experimental group's mean attitude score towards mathematics has no significant difference because it remained in the neutral range both before and after the intervention. It indicates that the slight decrease in the mean score from pre-test to post-test is not large enough to be considered a significant change. If students have a long-standing neutral or negative perception of math, gamification may not provide sufficient motivation or engagement to alter these views significantly (Attah et al., 2024). If students do not understand the value of mathematics in their daily life or future careers, they may remain uninterested despite gamification attempts. This view can lead to a lack of motivation to fully engage with mathematical subjects. Students have diverse learning styles and preferences; some may thrive in traditional learning environments while others benefit from interactive approaches. If gamification does not cater to individual preferences, it may fail to create a positive shift in attitudes (Antonio and Tamban, 2022).

The result was supported by the current study of Soybas (2019) which found no significant difference between the achievement and attitude scores of the students in the experimental and control groups.

Difference between the Attitudes of the Students towards Mathematics under the Experimental and Controlled Groups after the Intervention

Table 6 shows the difference between the attitudes of the students towards Mathematics under the experimental and controlled groups after the intervention.

Table 6. *Difference between the Attitude Towards Mathematics under the Experimental and Controlled Groups after the Intervention*

<i>Groups</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Control	33	3.27
Experimental	33	3.36

Computed value (z): -1.25

P-value: 0.210

Decision: Accept Ho

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the z-test for two sample means, Table 6 shows that the control group has a post-test mean score of 3.27, while the experimental group has a higher mean result of 3.36. The computed z-value of -1.25 and the associated p-value of 0.210 indicates that the observed difference in mean scores is not statistically significant. With a p-value of 0.210, which is greater than the typical significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

The data shows that the control group and the experimental group both falling within the neutral range. This means that participants from both groups neither strongly agreed nor disagreed with the statements or items being measured.

The result further implies that their attitudes remained the same after the intervention. This indicates that the intervention applied to the experimental group did not result in a significant shift in attitudes or responses compared to the control group. This clearly means that there is no evidence to suggest a significant difference in attitude toward math between the experimental and controlled groups

after the intervention.

However, it contradicted the research findings of Yildirim (2022) and Sun-Lin & Chiou (2021) that it can successfully promote attitude, other factors may have influenced these results. Since our current educational setting is distant, kids and teachers are still adjusting to the new normal. The home environment differs significantly from the school environment, which may have an impact on attitude and learning.

Difference between the Performance of the Students in the Experimental Group Before and After the Intervention

Table 7 below presents the difference between the academic performance of the students under the experimental group before and after the intervention.

Table 7. *Difference between the Academic Performance of the Students under the Experimental Group Before and After the Intervention*

Experimental Group	N	Mean
Pre-test	33	10.06
Post test	33	25.33

Computed value (z): -5.57
P-value: 0.001
Decision: Reject H_0
Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 7 reveals that the mean score increased from 10.06 in the pre-test to 25.33 in the post-test. With a computed value of -5.57 and a p-value of <0.001 which is lower than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the academic performance of the students under the experimental group before and after the intervention.

The result indicates a strong differences between the pre-test and post test scores. Therefore, the improvement of scores can be attributed to the intervention and is not due to random chance. It also indicates that gamification can be a powerful tool in enhancing educational outcomes. Students enjoy during the class activity using gamification and thus perform academically. Increased engagement and motivation through game elements can lead to better comprehension and retention of material. Active participation and instant feedback in gamification can enhance learning experiences.

This finding can be used to support the integration of game elements in educational practices to foster better engagement and performance.

This finding is in consonance with Chen et al. (2018) that it has been demonstrated that "gamified" active learning improves students' academic achievement. In previous years, extensive studies have been conducted on digital game-based learning. Academics from all fields of study concur that digital game-based learning is more effective than traditional lecture training at improving learning outcomes and motivating students to learn.

Difference between the Academic Performance of the Students Under Experimental and Controlled Groups After the Intervention

Table 8 shows the difference between the academic performance of the students under experimental and controlled groups after the intervention.

Table 8. *Difference between the Academic Performance of the Students under Experimental and Controlled Groups after the Intervention*

Groups	N	Mean
Experimental	33	25.33
Control	33	17.82

Computed value (z): 4.95
P-value: <0.001
Decision: Reject H_0
Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Table 8 shows that the experimental group's mean 25.33 was significantly greater than the control group's score of 17.82. Using the z-test, the computed value is 4.95 and the p-value of <0.001 is lower than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected. This means that there is a significant difference between the academic performance of students under the experimental and controlled groups after the intervention.

The result of this study implies that the intervention improved the experimental group's students' academic performance relative to the control group. It also indicates a positive impact of gamification to the performance of students. It also means that gamification is more effective than the discussion method. The result shows that discussion and dialogue learning may lead to lower engagement and interest.

This finding was supported by Tamban (2020) who posited that the experimental group significantly outperformed the control group in the pretest and posttest mean scores. It was claimed that even though the students who received gamification instruction did not considerably improve in terms of attitude, their performance did. As a result, gamification proved to be a successful teaching strategy in raising students' math proficiency in Grade 8.

Conclusions

Based on the findings the following conclusions were drawn:

There is no discernible difference in the experimental and control groups's attitudes toward Mathematics since both groups interpretations of the data was neutral.

Both the experimental and control groups exhibited enhancements in their academic performance from the pretest to the post test. The data indicates that the intervention had a more significant and positive impact on the academic performance of the experimental group compared to the control group.

The statistical analysis indicates that the slight decrease in the mean score from pre-test to post-test is not large enough to be considered a significant change.

Gamification did not lead to a significant difference in the attitude toward mathematics between the experimental and controlled

The results reveal a significant improvement in the academic performance of students in the experimental group after the intervention.

The intervention improved the experimental group's students' academic performance relative to the control group.

The study's findings and conclusions led to the following suggestions being made: Given that it has been demonstrated that gamification greatly enhances student performance, it is advised that:

Students may embrace the gamified learning experience with an open mind. Understand that gamification can make mathematics more enjoyable and engaging. Take an active role in the gamified activities, participating fully and striving to achieve goals and rewards. Use gamified platforms as supplementary tools for self-directed learning outside of the classroom to reinforce understanding of mathematical concepts.

Parents may encourage their children to explore gamified mathematics learning platforms and games that align with their interests and learning styles. Monitor their child's engagement with gamified learning activities and provide support and encouragement when needed. Recognize the value of gamification in improving your child's attitudes toward mathematics and supporting their academic performance.

Teachers can integrate gamification elements into mathematics lessons to increase student engagement and motivation. Provide clear instructions and objectives for gamified activities, ensuring that they align with learning objectives and curriculum standards. Offer opportunities for collaboration and peer interaction within gamified

School administrators may support teachers in implementing gamified learning approaches by providing professional development and resources. Allocate funding for the acquisition of gamified learning platforms and tools that can enhance mathematics education. Encourage collaboration and sharing of best practices among educators to optimize the effectiveness of gamification in the classroom.

Future Researchers can conduct longitudinal studies to assess the long-term effects of gamification on attitudes toward mathematics and academic performance. Investigate the optimal combination of gamification elements (e.g., rewards, challenges, social interactions) for different student demographics and learning contexts. Explore the potential of emerging technologies (e.g., virtual reality, artificial intelligence) to enhance gamified mathematics learning experiences. By implementing these recommendations, stakeholders can maximize the benefits of gamification in mathematics education for Grade 9 students, fostering positive attitudes and improving academic performance in the subject.

References

- Alova, C. a. R. (2019). Attitude towards mathematics in relation to academic performance of Grade 11 students. Zenodo (CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7236086>
- Astashova, N. A., Bondyreva, S. K., & Popova, O. S. (2023). Gamification resources in education: A theoretical approach. *Obrazovanie I Nauka*, 25(1), 15–49. <https://doi.org/10.17853/1994-5639-2023-1-15-49>
- Avcu, Y. E., & Er, K. O. (2020). Design thinking applications in teaching programming to gifted students. *Journal of Educational Technology and Online Learning*, 3(1), 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.31681/jetol.671621>
- Barrot, J. S., Llenares, I. I., & Del Rosario, L. S. (2021). Students' online learning challenges during the pandemic and how they cope with them: The case of the Philippines. *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(6), 7321–7338. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10589-x>

- Bicen, H., & Kocakoyun, S. (2018). Perceptions of Students for Gamification Approach: Kahoot as a Case study. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning/International Journal: Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 13(02), 72. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v13i02.7467>
- Cevher, A. Y., & Yildirim, S. (2020). Investigation of Academic Studies on Learning Styles: A Systematic review. *Hayef:Journal of Education*, 17(1), 20–50. <https://doi.org/10.5152/hayef.2020.1922>
- Davadas, S. D., & Fah, L. Y. (2021). *Contributing Factors Affecting Students Attitudes towards Mathematics in Sabah*. Universiti Malaysia Sabah Press.
- Deng, L., Wu, S., Chen, Y., & Peng, Z. (2020). Digital game-based learning in a Shanghai primary-school mathematics class: A case study. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 36(5), 709–717. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12438>
- Dowker, A., Cheriton, O., Horton, R., & Mark, W. (2019). Relationships between attitudes and performance in young children's mathematics. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 100(3), 211–230. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-019-9880-5>
- Garber, L. L., Hyatt, E. M., & Boya, Ü. Ö. (2018). Constituting, testing and validating the gender learner profiles of serious game participants. *International Journal of Management Education*, 16(2), 205–223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2018.02.005>
- Gök, M. (2020). Mathematical mystery in a cultural game. *World Journal of Education*, 10(6), 64. <https://doi.org/10.5430/wje.v10n6p64>
- Hopkins, L., Hampton, B. S., Abbott, J. F., Buery-Joyner, S. D., Craig, L. B., Dalrymple, J. L., Forstein, D. A., Graziano, S. C., McKenzie, M. L., Pradham, A., Wolf, A., & Page-Ramsey, S. M. (2018). To the point: medical education, technology, and the millennial learner. *American Journal of Obstetrics and Gynecology*, 218(2), 188–192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajog.2017.06.001>
- Hwang, S., & Son, T. (2021). Students' Attitude toward Mathematics and its Relationship with Mathematics Achievement. *Journal of Education and E-learning Research*, 8(3), 272–280. <https://doi.org/10.20448/journal.509.2021.83.272.280>
- Ismaizam, N. M., Rahman, S. F. A., Ahmad, S. N. S. M., Nazri, N. I. I. M., Idris, N. a. A., Ali, N. A., Rafi, N. F. B. M., Mohamad, S. N. A., Rahim, A. a. A., Rashid, K. K. A., & Aldaba, A. M. A. (2022). An Integration of Game-based learning in a Classroom: An Overview (2016 - 2021). *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarped/v11-i1/12347>
- Ke, F., & Clark, K. M. (2018). Game-Based multimodal representations and mathematical problem solving. *International Journal of Science and Mathematical Education/International Journal of Science and Mathematics Education*, 18(1), 103–122. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10763-018-9938-3>
- Kim, J., & Castelli, D. M. (2021). Effects of Gamification on Behavioral Change in Education: A Meta-Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health/International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(7), 3550. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18073550>
- Kirkpatrick, J. N., Mitchell, C., Taub, C., Kort, S., Hung, J., & Swaminathan, M. (2020). ASE Statement on Protection of Patients and Echocardiography Service Providers during the 2019 novel Coronavirus Outbreak: endorsed by the American College of Cardiology. *Journal of the American Society of Echocardiography*, 33(6), 648–653. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.echo.2020.04.001>
- Kumar, S., Agarwal, M., & Agarwal, N. (2021). Defining and Measuring Academic Performance of HEI Students-A Critical Review. *Türk Bilgisayar Ve Matematik Eğitimi Dergisi*, 12(6), 3091–3105. <https://turcomat.org/index.php/turkbilmamat/article/view/6952>
- Lamrani, R., & Abdelwahed, E. (2020). Game-based learning and gamification to improve skills in early years education. *Computer Science and Information Systems*, 17(1), 339–356. <https://doi.org/10.2298/csis1905110431>
- Lanuza, M. H. (2020). Integrative Gamification technique in teaching specialization courses in mathematics. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(4), 1275–1281. <https://www.ijstr.org/final-print/apr2020/Integrative-Gamification-Technique-In-Teaching-Specialization-Courses-In-Mathematics.pdf>
- Laranang, J. a. I., & Bondoc, J. M. F. (2020). Attitudes and Self- Efficacy of Students toward Mathematics. *International Journal of English, Literature and Social Science*, 5(5), 1392–1423. <https://doi.org/10.22161/ijels.55.11>
- León-Mantero, C., Casas-Rosal, J. C., Pedrosa-Jesús, C., & Maz-Machado, A. (2020b). Measuring attitude towards mathematics using Likert scale surveys: The weighted average. *PloSOne*, 15(10), e0239626. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0239626>
- Lima, M. a. S., Monteiro, Á. C., Leite, A. J. M., Junior, De Andrade Matos, I. S., Alexandre, F. S. O., Nobre, D. J., Monteiro, A. J., & Da Silva Júnior, J. N. (2019). Game-Based application for helping students review chemical nomenclature in a fun way. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 96(4), 801–805. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.8b00540>
- Liu, Z., Shaikh, Z. A., & Gazizova, F. (2020). Using the concept of Game-Based Learning in education. *International Journal of*

- Emerging Technologies in Learning/International Journal: Emerging Technologies in Learning, 15(14), 53. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i14.14675>
- Manzano-León, A., Camacho-Lazarraga, P., Guerrero, M. A., Guerrero-Puerta, L., Aguilar-Parra, J. M., Trigueros, R., & Alias, A. (2021). Between level up and game over: A Systematic Literature Review of Gamification in Education. *Sustainability*, 13(4), 2247. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13042247>
- Mazana, M. Y., Montero, C. S., & Casmir, R. O. (2018). Investigating Students' Attitude towards Learning Mathematics. *International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.29333/iejme/3997>
- Mondido, (2018). Effect of Problem-based learning to Performance in Mathematics of Grade 9 and Grade 10. La Carlota City College Graduate School.
- Mylonas, G., Paganelli, F., Cuffaro, G., Nesi, I., & Karantzis, D. (2021). Using gamification and IoT-based educational tools towards energy savings - some experiences from two schools in Italy and Greece. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence & Humanized Computing/Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, 14(12), 15725–15744. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-020>
- Nieto-Escamez, F. A., & Roldán-Tapia, M. D. (2021). Gamification as Online Teaching Strategy During COVID-19: A Mini-Review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.648552>
- PISA 2018 Results (Volume I). (2019). In Programme for international student assessment/Internationale Schulleistungsstudie. <https://doi.org/10.1787/5f07c754-en>
- Quaye, J. (2020). Attitudes Towards Mathematics And Mathematical Achievement In Secondary Schools In England: Exploring The Role Of Social Class, Gender And Ethnicity. *Lulu.Com.Journals*
- Quaye, J., & Pomeroy, D. (2021). Social class inequalities in attitudes towards mathematics and achievement in mathematics cross generations: a quantitative Bourdieusian analysis. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 109(1), 155–175. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-021-10078-5>
- Realyvásquez-Vargas, A., Maldonado-Macías, A. A., Arredondo-Soto, K. C., Baez-Lopez, Y., Carrillo-Gutiérrez, T., & Hernández-Escobedo, G. (2020). The Impact of Environmental Factors on Academic Performance of University Students Taking Online Classes during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Mexico. *Sustainability*, 12(21), 9194. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12219194>
- Rincon-Flores, E. G., Velarde-Camaqui, D., Santos-Guevara, B., Rodríguez-Rodríguez, N., Quintana-Cruz, H., & Matsuura-Sonoda, A. (2022). IMPROVING ATTITUDES TOWARD MATHEMATICS THROUGH GAMIFICATION. *ICERI Proceedings*. <https://doi.org/10.21125/iceri.2022.1486>
- Ruiperez-Valiente, J. A., Gaydos, M., Rosenheck, L., Kim, Y. J., & Klopfer, E. (2020). Patterns of engagement in an educational massively multiplayer online game: A Multidimensional view. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 13(4), 648–661. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tlt.2020.2968234>
- Sailer, M., & Sailer, M. (2020). Gamification of in-class activities in flipped classroom lectures. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 52(1), 75–90. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12948>
- Sarkar, A., & Roy, T. S. (2023). Creation and Development of a Digital Game for use of Gamification as a Teaching-Learning Approach in Mathematics: a Secondary level research. *Actualidades Pedagógicas/Actualidades Pedagógicas*. <https://doi.org/10.19052/ap.vol1.iss79.6>
- Sima, V., Gheorghe, I. G., Subić, J., & Nancu, D. (2020). Influences of the Industry 4.0 Revolution on the human capital Development and Consumer Behavior: A Systematic review. *Sustainability*, 12(10), 4035. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12104035>
- Smiderle, R., Rigo, S. J., Marques, L. B., De Miranda Coelho, J. a. P., & Jaques, P. A. (2020). The impact of gamification on students' learning, engagement, and behavior based on their personality traits. *Smart Learning Environments*, 7(1) <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-019-0098-x>
- Smiderle, R., Rigo, S. J., Marques, L. B., De Miranda Coelho, J. a. P., & Jaques, P. A. (2020). The impact of gamification on students' learning, engagement and behavior based on their personality traits. *Smart Learning Environments*, 7(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-019-0098-x>
- Subia, G. S., Salangang, L. G., & Medrano, H. B. (2018). Attitude and Performance in Mathematics I of Bachelor of Elementary Education Students: A Correlational Analysis. *American Scientific Research Journal for Engineering, Technology, and Sciences*, 39(1), 206–213. https://asrjetsjournal.org/index.php/American_Scientific_Journal/article/download/3821/1378
- Sun-Lin, H. Z., & Chiou, G. F. (2019). Effects of gamified comparison on sixth graders' algebra word problem solving and learning attitude. *DOAJ (DOAJ: Directory of Open Access Journals)*. <https://doaj.org/article/18265ea872bf4b78a2b4b9a649308afc>

Tokac, U., Novak, E., & Thompson, C. G. (2019). Effects of game-based learning on students' mathematics achievement: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning*, 35(3), 407–420. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12347>

Toquero, C. M. (2020). Emergency remote education experiment amid COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Educational Research and Innovation*, 15, 162–176. <https://doi.org/10.46661/ijeri.5113>

Wakhata, R., Mutarutinya, V., & Balimuttajjo, S. (2022). Secondary school students' attitude towards mathematics word problems. *Humanities & Social Sciences Communications*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-022-01449-1>

Yaşar, S. (2018). The Role of Massively Multiplayer Online Role-Playing Games in Extramural Second Language Learning: A literature review. *Journal of Educational Technology and Online Learning*, 1(3), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.31681/jetol.436100>

Zamir, S., Yang, Z., Wenwu, H., & Sarwar, U. (2022). Assessing the attitude and problem-based learning in mathematics through PLS-SEM modeling. *PloS One*, 17(5), e0266363. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0266363>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jesalyn M. Lazarte, LPT

La Carlota City College – Philippines

Sharon L. Apohen, PhD

La Carlota City College – Philippines